

A Survey on Consumer Preference for Handcrafted Cellphone Lanyards Among Grade 12 Students in Crossing Bayabas National High School

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Abstract. The study employed a descriptive research design to investigate consumer preferences for handcrafted cellphone lanyards among Grade 12 students at Crossing Bayabas National High School during the academic year 2023-2024 as an educational and business research. Through stratified random sampling, 100 Grade 12 students were recruited, ensuring representation from each academic strand. Data were gathered through a survey checklist of 14 items, validated by three experts. Responses were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages. The study found that many students, especially those aged 18 to 20 and female, like handcrafted cellphone lanyards. They prefer mixed colors and style over comfort. Wooden bead designs are popular, and most students prefer paying with cash. 73% said they would likely buy the lanyards. The findings suggest a promising market opportunity for these products. To capitalize on this interest, it is recommended to focus on producing lanyards with diverse color options and appealing designs, emphasizing individuality and style. Additionally, offering cash payment options and exploring avenues for promoting the product's unique features could further enhance its appeal and increase sales potential.

KEY WORDS

1. consumer preference
2. handcrafted lanyards
3. ABM strand
4. Crossing Bayabas National High School

1. Introduction

Handcrafted cellphone lanyards are accessories popular nowadays. Various demographics and organizations, including schools, use lanyards (Carvey Hage, 2021; Dewies et al., 2021; Izudi et al., 2017; Willems Warren, 2020). For several reasons, it is essential to understand the consumer preferences for these lanyards among senior high school students.

Firstly, studying consumer preferences provides valuable insights into the purchasing decisions among students. Researchers must identify the design elements, materials, and features that appeal to students' demographics.

Secondly, exploring consumer preferences can aid in the development of marketing strategies. Manufacturers can attract lanyard markets through targeted and effective campaigns (Newmeyer et al., 2021). Senior high school can be one targeted market.

The study on consumer preferences for handcrafted cellphone lanyards can also contribute to consumer behavior research (Ismagilova et al., 2020; Malter et al., 2020; Shen et al., 2021). In this study, researchers examined how demographics, such as age, sex, and weekly allowance, can influence the choice of lanyards in the context of design, color, and logo.

Moreover, this Crossing Bayabas National High School study offers a localized perspective on consumer preferences. Focusing on a specific school and demographic, the researchers gathered detailed and relevant data. These data can inform local businesses and craftsmen about the demand for handcrafted lanyards in the area (Chien, 2019; Sugimoto Nagasawa, 2017; Swift, 2020).

One theory that underpins this study is the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991). This theory focuses on understanding and predicting human behavior based on three key factors: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. In the context of this study, the TPB could help explain why students choose specific designs, colors, or materials for their lanyards. They based their choices on their attitudes towards these features, the influence of subjective norms (such as peer preferences or fashion trends), and their perceived control over their purchasing decisions (like availability of funds or accessibility to the product). Integrating the TPB into the study's framework can provide a theoretical basis for analyzing and interpreting the factors driving consumer preferences among Grade 12 students.

While there have been several studies regarding lanyards, those studies were about the adverse effects of using lanyards, especially in the healthcare sector (Abd elsaour Kinawy et al., 2024; Decker Clancy, 2021; Draper, 2024; French, 2018; Murphy et al., 2017). The absence of prior research highlights the need for a comprehensive understanding of Grade 12 students' preferences for handcrafted lanyards. By filling this gap, this study can contribute valuable insights into consumer behavior and marketing, especially concerning young consumers and product categories.

Overall, this study addresses a significant gap in the literature by investigating consumer preferences for handcrafted cellphone lanyards among Grade 12 students at Crossing Bayabas National High School. The findings will contribute to academic knowledge and the practical implications for businesses and marketers targeting this demographic.

1.1. Research Questions—Importantly, this study aimed to determine students' preferences regarding handcrafted cellphone lanyards. Specifically, it explored answers to the following questions:

- (1) What is the percentage of respondents within these aspects of their profile?
 - (1) Age
 - (2) Sex
 - (3) Allowance
- (2) What is the percentage preference for handcrafted cellphone lanyards in terms of:
 - (1) Colors
 - (2) Features
 - (3) Materials
 - (4) Mode of Payment
 - (5) Logo, and
 - (6) Design?
- (3) What is the percentage of demand for cellphone lanyards among Grade 12 students at Crossing Bayabas National High School?

The findings of this study are significant for businesses, marketers, educators, local crafts workers, and the academic community. Each can derive specific benefits and insights relevant to their respective interests and objectives.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design, sample, instruments, data collection procedure, and data analysis plan.

2.1. Research Design—The study employed a descriptive research design to investigate consumer preferences for handcrafted cellphone lanyards among Grade 12 students. This design describes and explores variables without manipulation (Pandey Pandey, 2021; Siedlecki, 2020). The study used percentages to provide a comprehensive overview of students' preferences.

In line with the descriptive design, the researchers designed a survey tool to collect data. They crafted the tool to gather detailed insights into the design elements, materials, features, and other factors. Additionally, adopting a descriptive approach depicts the consumer landscape accurately. It provides valuable information for businesses, educators, and researchers interested in this specialized market segment.

2.2. Research Sample—The researchers recruited 100 Grade 12 students through stratified random sampling. These students were from Crossing Bayabas National High School during the academic year 2023-2024. The stratified random sampling ensured representation from each academic strand. Calculating the 10 percent population of Grade 12 students yielded approximately 94 students. Bullen (2013) claimed that 100 sample size can yield meaningful results in statistical analysis. To align with Bullen's claim, the researchers added six samples. These six samples came from each academic strand. This adjustment aimed to maintain a robust sample size. Also, to account for the practicalities of research implementation within the school's context.

2.3. The Instrument—The researchers used a survey questionnaire as an instrument for data gathering. The survey questionnaires underwent validation by three validators. Follow-

ing validation, the survey questionnaires were distributed for pilot testing. The tool used for data gathering was a checklist format, allowing respondents to tick their desired choices. For instance, under the "Profile" section, respondents could indicate their age (in brackets), select their sex (options included male and female), and specify their weekly allowances (also in brackets). Regarding consumer preferences, the checklist covered aspects such as colors, features, materials used, mode of payment, logo preferences, and design elements. Additionally, under the "Demand" section, respondents were asked whether they would purchase the product if it were available in the market, with response options including "Yes," "No," and "Maybe."

2.4. Data Collection Procedure—The researchers followed these steps in conducting this study:

2.4.1. Seeking Permission to Conduct the Study—The researchers drafted a formal letter addressed to the Crossing Bayabas National High School principal, seeking permission to conduct the study. The letter was duly noted and endorsed by the thesis adviser.

2.4.2. The Preparation of the Questionnaire—The researchers created a questionnaire to assess Consumers' Preferences for Handcrafted Cellphone Lanyards at Crossing Bayabas National High School. This instrument underwent validation by three (3) research experts from the school. The Evaluation Sheet included criteria such as focus on the study, cohesiveness, alignment with learner needs, inclusivity of items, correlation, comprehensibility of input, and study aims. Feedback and suggestions provided by the evaluators were used to revise and refine the questionnaire.

2.4.3. *Test Administration, Retrieval, and Recording*—The researchers personally administered the instruments to the identified respondents, after which they retrieved the completed questionnaires. Subsequently, the researchers recorded the responses and conducted data analysis using SPSS. The researchers used pie graphs because they were working with percentages exclusively.

2.5. *Data Analysis Plan*—A quantitative approach was employed in this study. Data

analysis played a crucial role, allowing the researchers to draw conclusions from the findings. The researchers analyzed responses to 14 items using data graphs and interpreted the percentages and the number of respondents who selected specific choices. They also identified the most and least popular choices for each survey question. The researchers reported the results using graphical representations.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of the study. As previously mentioned, the researchers utilized graphic representations to report the findings, aligning with the research questions. The following section outlines the key results and findings obtained from the study

3.1. Profile of Respondents—

3.1.1. *Age of Respondents*—The graph indicates that half of the respondents, totaling 50 (50percent), fall within the age range of 18-20

years old. Those aged 15-17 account for 35 respondents (35percent), while 15 (15percent) are 20 years old and above. Thus, most of the respondents belong to the 18-20 age group.

3.1.2. *Sex of Respondents*—The graph illustrates that 61 respondents (61percent) identified as female, while 39 (39percent) identified

otherwise. This result indicates that females constituted the majority of respondents who participated in the survey.

3.1.3. *Weekly Allowance of Respondents*—According to the depicted graph, 32percent (32percent) of respondents reported having a weekly allowance of Php351 and above. This was followed by 29percent (29percent) of re-

spondents who indicated a weekly allowance of Php51 to Php100. Additionally, 28percent (28percent) of respondents reported a weekly allowance between Php251 and Php350, while 11percent (11percent) stated a weekly allowance ranging from Php101 to Php250.

The results indicate that handcrafted cell-phone lanyards may be particularly popular among young adults aged 18-20 at Crossing Bayabas National High School, with females constituting the majority of interested respondents. Additionally, the distribution of weekly allowances suggests potential market segments with varying purchasing power, with higher allowances indicating a potential for premium or higher-priced lanyard designs and lower allowances highlighting the importance of offering affordable options to cater to a broader range of respondents. These implications can guide

businesses, designers, and marketers in tailoring their products, pricing strategies, and marketing efforts to effectively target the preferences and purchasing capacity of the school’s student population.

3.2. Preferences of Grade 12 Students for Handcrafted Lanyards—

3.2.1. Color—The graph reveals that 40percent (40percent) of respondents prefer mixed colors for their lanyards, while 31percent (31 percent) opt for light colors, and 29 percent (29 percent) prefer dark colors.

3.2.2. Features—According to the graph below, style appears to be the top priority for most respondents, with 35 percent (35 percent) selecting it as their primary consideration. Com-

fort follows closely at 33 percent (33 percent), while quality ranks third at 19 percent (19 percent), and durability is chosen by 13 percent (13 percent) of respondents.

3.2.3. Materials Used—According to the graph below, wooden beads are the most preferred choice among respondents, with 28 percent (28percent) selecting them. Abaca follows

closely at 27 percent (27 percent), trailed by shells at 25 percent (25 percent), macrame at 12 percent (12 percent), and waterproof paper beads at 8 percent (8 percent).

Colors

Features preferred

Materials to be used

Mode of payment

3.2.4. *Mode of payment*—According to the graph below, most respondents prefer paying through cash rather than using Gcash. Specifically,

79 percent (79 percent) of respondents favor meetups as their payment method, while Gcash is chosen by 21 percent (21 percent) of respondents.

3.2.5. *Logo*—Based on the graph above, it is evident that the third logo is the most preferred among respondents, with 40 percent (40

percent) selecting it. In comparison, both the first and second logos garnered equal preference, each receiving 30 percent (30 percent) of the respondents' choices.

Logo

3.2.6. *Design*—According to the graph, 40 percent (40 percent) of respondents selected mixed beads as their preferred lanyard de-

sign/style. Minimalist followed this closely at 39 percent (39 percent), and sequence at 29 percent (29 percent).

3.2.7. *Demand for Handcrafted Lanyards*—The graph indicates that a significant majority of respondents, 73 percent (73 percent), are inclined to purchase the proposed product. This high percentage of positive responses reflects a strong demand for the product among the surveyed respondents. Additionally, 20 percent (20

percent) of respondents who indicated "maybe" suggested potential interest that could be further cultivated with targeted marketing or product enhancements. While a small percentage, 7 percent (7 percent), responded negatively, focusing on the substantial positive response is crucial, indicating a promising market for the product.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the key findings derived from the data analysis and interpretation. It offers insights into the preferences, trends, and behaviors observed among the respondents. Additionally, based on these conclusions, the chapter provides actionable recommendations. Stakeholders, designers, marketers, and educators can leverage the study’s findings to enhance their strategies, products, and services.

4.1. *Conclusion*—1. The study on consumer preferences for handcrafted cellphone lanyards among Grade 12 students has revealed valuable insights. Most respondents, particularly young adults aged 18-20, may show a strong interest in these products. Females constitute a significant portion of potential customers. Furthermore, the analysis of weekly allowances suggests varying purchasing power among respondents. It highlighted the need for a diverse product range to cater to different budget preferences. These findings significantly affect businesses, designers, and marketers in tailoring their strategies. For instance, targeting young adults, particularly females, with stylish and affordable lanyard designs could capture a substantial market share. Additionally, businesses can offer premium options for those with higher allowances because they can afford the product.

2. The findings reveal that many respondents prefer mixed colors (40 percent) for their lanyards. Students prefer vibrant and varied designs. Style emerges as the top priority (35 percent) among features considered by respondents. They preferred aesthetics in the lanyard selection. When it comes to materials used, wooden beads (28 percent) are favored, followed closely by abaca (27 percent) and shells (25 percent). These results indicated a preference for natural and visually appealing materials. Regarding payment methods, cash payment during meetups is the preferred choice (79 percent). It denoted a preference for traditional and face-to-face transactions over digital options like Gcash (21 percent). Regarding the logo, the third logo stands out as the most preferred (40 percent) among respondents. It suggested the importance of a visually appealing and recognizable brand identity. Mixed beads (40 percent) are the preferred style in terms of design. Although others like minimalist (39 percent) and sequined (29 percent) designs.

3. The data reveals the respondents' robust

demand for handcrafted lanyards. 73 percent indicated a willingness to purchase the product. This solid positive response underscores the market potential and consumer interest in handcrafted lanyards. The 20 percent of respondents expressed a "maybe" response. The "maybe" response signals an opportunity to further cultivate interest through targeted marketing strategies or product enhancements. Although there is a small 7 percent negative response, the focus should remain on the significant positive feedback. This result indicates a promising market outlook for the product.

This study is a foundation for informed decision-making and strategic planning. It offers valuable insights into the changing needs and preferences of Grade 12 students at Crossing Bayabas National High School. The conclusions drawn from the study can guide businesses and designers in creating products that align closely with the preferences and expectations of this target market. Additionally, these findings can enhance market competitiveness and increase customer satisfaction. Getting into the details of these insights can help people in business make informed decisions. They develop strategic plans to effectively meet the demands of Grade 12 students, ultimately driving success in the handcrafted lanyard market.

4.2. *Recommendations*—1. In light of these findings, it is recommended that businesses pull the popularity of handcrafted cellphone lanyards among Grade 12 students. They can do that by creating appealing designs that align with their preferences. Moreover, businesses can implement flexible pricing strategies to accommodate varying budget levels and market competitiveness.

2. To align with Grade 12 students' preferences for handcrafted lanyards, businesses should diversify color options. They can emphasize aesthetic appeal with trendy designs and natural materials like wood and abaca. They can also offer flexible payment methods like cash

and digital options like Gcash. They may also invest in a strong brand identity with visually appealing logos and versatile designs. Moreover, they can engage with the target market through regular feedback and involvement in product development processes. These strategies can enhance customer satisfaction, market competitiveness, and overall business growth in the handcrafted lanyard industry.

3. Businesses may capitalize on this opportunity based on the high demand indicated by the survey results. They can optimize marketing efforts for vast market reach. They can have advertising campaigns promoting handcrafted lanyards' unique features and benefits. These can attract more customers and convert "maybe" respondents into buyers. Additionally, continuous product improvement and innovation based on customer feedback can further enhance the appeal of handcrafted lanyards. These can make

handcrafted lanyards a preferred choice among consumers.

4. Future researchers can explore deeper demographic analysis to gain a comprehensive view of consumer preferences among Grade 12 students regarding handcrafted lanyards. They can explore socioeconomic status, cultural background, and geographic location. Future researchers can also incorporate qualitative research methods. They can do interviews or focus groups to get detailed insights into underlying motivations and decision-making processes. Additionally, they can conduct longitudinal studies over extended periods and stay updated with market trends. They can evaluate various marketing strategies to enhance the relevance and impact of future research in understanding and catering to evolving consumer needs and preferences in this specialized market segment.

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